

The Covenant Ceremony in the Community Rule (1QS)

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Data source: Prayer in the Ancient World

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Abrahamic, Canaanite, Ritual text, Jewish Traditions, Semitic, Prayer, Dead Sea Scrolls, Text, Northwest Semitic, Afro-Asiatic, Central Semitic, West Semitic, Language, Late Second Temple Judaism, Early Jewish Literature, Hebrewic, Ancient Hebrew, Judaism

The Covenant Ceremony is a section of the Community Rule (1QS 1:16-2:18), one of the Dead Sea Scrolls. It is an initiation ceremony for members joining the community and a reminder of group boundaries and beliefs for those who have previously joined the group. The ceremony itself consists of three parts: a description of the community which the initiates join (referred to as the order of the yahad) and a blessing of God; a description of God's deeds for Israel (led by the priests) and the sins of Israel (led by the Levites) to which the initiates respond with confession of their own sins and priests bless God's lot and the Levites curse Belial's lot; and a statement regarding the priests' and the Levites' cursing those who come to the covenant ceremony with impure or false motives. The initiates assent to the conclusion of each major section of the ceremony with a collective "Amen, amen." There is no specific timing for the ritual's performance described within the text, but textual references hint that it may have taken place during the festival of weeks, which is associated with covenant-making traditions. The ceremony pairs blessings and confessions to ensure that those who join the covenant with pure heart and mind receive the blessing and those who do not are cursed. Only those initiated into the community via the ceremony were able to access purification and atonement from their God. The best manuscript of the Covenant Ceremony is the Community Rule (S) 1QS 1:16-2:18, though fragments with parallel textual material have been found in other manuscripts (4Q256, 4Q257, and 5Q11). All texts of the Covenant Ceremony are written in Hebrew, and all but 4Q257 (which is written on papyrus) are leather scrolls. Extant manuscripts are dated to the first century BCE. There are no variants in the textual material across these manuscripts but the material is poorly preserved. This text bears similarities to other covenant ceremonies, but is unique in its pairing of blessings, curses, and the role of the priests and Levites.

Date Range: 100 BCE - 0 CE

Region: Jewish settlement during the Second Temple period, probably at Qumran

Region tags: Israel, Palestine, Middle East, Qumran, Israel in the Second Temple period

Jewish settlement during the late Second Temple period, probably at the site of Qumran

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Jokiranta, Jutta. "Covenant Ceremony." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: brill.com/display/serial/PAMW?language=en

Notes: Jokiranta, Jutta. "Covenant Ceremony." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <http://dss.collections.imj.org.il/>

- Source 1 Description: Digital Dead Sea Scrolls, hosted by the Israel Museum, Jerusalem

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Inked

- with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Other textile: 1QS, 4Q256, and 5Q11 are leather scrolls, while 4Q257 is preserved on papyrus.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Tomb

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Cemetery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Temple

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Shrine

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Altar

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Devotional marker

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Church

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Mosque

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Synagogue

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ **Monument**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ **Mass Gathering Point**

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ **Cave(s)**

– Yes

Notes: The Community Rule manuscripts containing the Covenant Ceremony, in part or in whole, were found in Caves 1, 4, and 5 of the caves near Qumran.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ **Hilltops**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ **Other natural sanctuaries**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ **Boundary markers or lines**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ **Domestic contexts**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: The text is one of many documents found in the caves near Qumran, which are known as the Dead Sea Scrolls.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Specify

– Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: However, it was probably considered authoritative by the community who wrote, copied, and preserved it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Notes: The text is written in Hebrew.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: The dialect is characteristic of the Hebrew of the Dead Sea Scrolls, and appears to be influenced by Aramaic.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

– Other [specify]: Torah was believed to be transmitted by Moses in Hebrew.

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: Possibly, since Greek and Aramaic scrolls have been found among the Dead Sea Scrolls.

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not contain the complete ritual. Therefore, oral traditions must have existed to instruct the priests and Levites on the performance of the ceremony.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The field can only estimate number of those within the Qumran Community (perhaps 75-150), but the Covenant Ceremony would include all those who are being initiated into the yahad, as well as previous initiates, and the priests and Levites.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: However, the group stressed the importance to join the covenant, and announced ritual practices outside their covenant as non-effective.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: The religious group itself represents a reformist movement within Judaism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Notes: The audience, the initiates to the Qumran movement, receive the blessings described within the ceremony from the Jewish God and enter into the order of the yahad.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ On the reciter?

– No

Notes: Aside from the implicit affirmation of group boundaries, no.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is it read?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The ritual is an initiation ceremony for those joining (or annually re-joining) the covenant of the Qumran movement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The community at Qumran consisted of perhaps 75-150 people. However, the so-called Qumran movement may have been larger, if consisted of small groups living in different places.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The number of participants is unknown. Covenant entry may also have taken place by taking an oath and did not require this ceremony (or was confirmed in the ceremony).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: The manuscripts do not explicitly mention a time for the ritual, but references hint that it may have taken place annually during the festival of the weeks.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: Proper belief and ritual adherence was an important feature of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: movement, but specific ritual praxis is not outlined in this section of text. Elsewhere specific legal rules are given, e.g., on Sabbath, purity, marriage, oaths, meetings, etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: Various groups (priest, Levites, people) recite and "enter" synchronically in groups.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Notes: However, in small group meetings, meals took place, so it is a possibility in covenant ceremony as well.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Covenant Ceremony is best preserved in the Community Rule (1QS), but it has parallel fragments recorded across several other manuscripts - all viewed as proper within the Qumran community with little variation. However, other manuscripts may include other type of ceremonies (e.g., 4Q286 Blessings) that have some similarities to Covenant Ceremony in 1QS.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: We do not know if different small groups used different versions of the text. Not all groups may have known the 1QS-version of the ceremony.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

Notes: One copy is written on papyrus; the others on leather scrolls. 4Q257 may preserve a longer version or have more space than the other copies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text is one of many collectively referred to as the Dead Sea Scrolls. Of course, this is a title assigned to the texts by the academic community and not the community who produced/copied/stored the texts. The texts were all found in caves near the site of Qumran.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Notes: However, this sectarian document was probably considered authoritative by the community who used it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Notes: However, 1QS-1QSa-1QSB is a manuscript that clearly includes different sections, possibly works.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: It is part of the collection of texts stored in the caves near Qumran, now known as the Dead Sea Scrolls.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: Yes if rule texts were meant to prescribe behavior.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Notes: Possibly rules and instruction for the movement's leader figures.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The text is not a ritual manual, but contains speech to be performed during a ritual (the covenant ceremony).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: However, priests represent a group with lineage from Aaron. Elsewhere in the Dead Sea Scrolls reference is made to the "Sons of Light" (God's elect) and the "Sons of Darkness."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: However, elsewhere in IQS there is a penal code on behavior in the assemblies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: However, the ritual described in the text may have been performed annually, perhaps as part of the feast of weeks. Other scrolls testify to the importance of 364-day calendar.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: However, there is a reference to "spirit" in the third section of the text. It is unclear whether this spirit is separable from the body. IQS 3-4 has a discourse on the two spirits (falsehood and truth), whose doings have effect on human lives and fate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: There is mention of "everlasting" destruction, which may imply a belief in an afterlife in which one could be either eternally blessed or cursed. However, this is not explicated, and the language may also refer to thisworldly fate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: However, a large cemetery exists next to the building complex at Qumran. No specific funerary texts survive.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: God and Belial are present in the text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

Notes: God is not associated with the sky in this text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

Notes: God has elected the faithful members of the community for blessing and knowledge.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Notes: The text does not state this explicitly, but it seems to be implied.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: God has the power to bless and curse people for eternity.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: The text is particularly concerned with what is in the hearts/minds of the initiates.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Can be hurt?
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Can be tricked?
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– No

Notes: Not described in this text.

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

Notes: Not described in this text.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of God.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Notes: This is not specified in the text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Here, I am referring to Belial, whose followers are cursed throughout the Covenant Ceremony.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Whether Belial has future knowledge is not clarified in this text. God has future knowledge.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: God effects the world. It is unclear whether Belial can reward and punish.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

Notes: However, study of sacred texts can be seen as ways of receiving revelation for the present.

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Belial leads people astray and away from God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: Exactly what Belial's status is in relation to God is unclear. He seems to be a lesser divine being. In other scrolls, divine beings are referred to as praising God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: However, his presence could be at least vividly imagined and perhaps experienced in some other liturgical texts, referring to worship in the heavenly temple.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are other categories of beings present?

– Paranormal?

Notes: Belial

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

Notes: Taboos are not specifically mentioned in this text. Yet in general, purity rules are also about taboos and what should be avoided (how impurity/disease spread by touching).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text. However, another rule document, the Damascus Document, is criticizing sexual practices.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: Entering the covenant with a false heart is condemned.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: Oath-taking is not mentioned in covenant ceremony but otherwise the commitment taken had to be sincere.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

Notes: Initiates are urged not to give into fear.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Notes: Respect of the priests and Levites and community are required.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text, yet elsewhere in 1QS false testimony is a concern.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text. Yet, elsewhere in 1QS lying about property is an issue.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text. Yet, in other scrolls (Damascus Document), wealth was considered potentially sinful.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text. However, refusal to join the covenant makes any ritual purification ineffective, and ritual purity rules were partly connected to matters that could be considered associated to hygiene (menstruation, semen, disease, contact to corpses).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Adherence to community rules, searching for divine knowledge.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: However, criteria for receiving punishment remain vague (e.g. wickedness, evil).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Notes: However, initiates to the covenant are also meant to confess their sins and thus reflect on their doings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Other

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: These punishments are vague in covenant ceremony but a longer list is found in IQS 4.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Political failure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

Notes: However, possibly, if covenant curses are understood as in biblical texts as all sorts of failure in one's efforts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

Notes: However, possibly, if covenant curses are understood as in biblical texts as all sorts of failure in one's efforts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

Notes: However, possibly, if covenant curses are understood as in biblical texts as all sorts of failure in one's efforts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not mention this explicitly, but mentions all the curses of the covenant as punishment: these may be a reference to curses in the Torah (e.g., Deut. 28).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

Notes: The text does not mention this explicitly, but mentions all the curses of the covenant as punishment: these may be a reference to curses in the Torah (e.g., Deut. 28).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

Notes: Rewards are vague in covenant ceremony but a longer list of healing, peace, long life, multiple progeny, and joy is found in 1QS 4.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

Notes: However, possibly, if covenant blessings are understood as in biblical texts as all sorts of success in one's efforts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

Notes: However, possibly, if covenant blessings are understood as in biblical texts as all sorts of success in one's efforts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

Notes: However, possibly, if covenant blessings are understood as in biblical texts as all sorts of success in one's efforts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

Notes: A blessed person is a healthy person.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Other?

– Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: However, elsewhere in 1QS is expectation of priestly, royal and prophetic Messiahs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text references the "reign of Belial" and the time to follow.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Field doesn't know

↳ At specified time in future

– Yes

Notes: At the end of Belial's rule. Elsewhere in the scrolls, there are more specific expectations, e.g., in relation to the periods of time.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future
 - No
- ↳ At some other time [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
 - Notes: Not clear in this text, but in general the movement though it had a crucial role of revealing the end.
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
 - Notes: Elsewhere in scrolls there is expectation of new rule for the temple of Jerusalem.
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: God's chosen ones rule.
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive
 - No
 - ↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– No

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

– Specify: Those elected by God will survive.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: However, the beginning of 1QS 1 and the penal code in 1QS includes social norms.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

Notes: However, 1QS 5 speaks of many virtues (e.g., truth, humility, charity, justice, lovingkindness, modesty).

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

Notes: However, 1QS 5 speaks of many virtues (e.g., truth, humility, charity, justice, lovingkindness, modesty).

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

Notes: However, 1QS 5 speaks of many virtues (e.g., truth, humility, charity, justice, lovingkindness, modesty).

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

Notes: However, 1QS 5 speaks of many virtues (e.g., truth, humility, charity, justice, lovingkindness, modesty).

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

Notes: However, IQS 5 speaks of many virtues (e.g., truth, humility, charity, justice, lovingkindness, modesty).

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

Notes: However, especially the wisdom teacher was expected to be able to discern between good and bad and spirits of people.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Notes: Not specifically mentioned in this text.

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge and search for wisdom.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: However, traditionally some scholars suggested that the community at Qumran was celibate. The text does not explicitly rule about it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: However, other rules (Damascus Document) does.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: However, other scrolls do (kosher rules).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: However, elsewhere rules (IQS and Damascus Document) speak of handing of property into communal funds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: However, it may have been risky for some members to attend the covenant ceremony if they travelled from far or a large gathering was considered a threat.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Notes: Yes - given that the text allows official membership within a sectarian religious community of the broader Jewish tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: However, the Qumran movement members may have assembled in smaller groups in household settings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The covenant ceremony took place annually but nothing is said about how long it lasted.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: Initiates are somehow ranked.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: The covenant ceremony may have been also a place to excommunicate members (Damascus Document).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: The priests, the Levites and the people probably entered in hierarchical groups and were ranked; liturgical words may have been recited together,

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Spiritual Elect

Notes: The religious group would likely describe itself as a spiritual/faith elect. They are a sectarian Jewish religious group of indeterminate size that probably lived near the caves in which the text was found, at the site of Qumran, as well as elsewhere in Judea.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The texts have not been reproduced beyond the original manuscripts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: However, other scrolls include social welfare help for widows and orphans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: However, 1QSa (attached to 1QS) is concerned that disabilities do not prevent people from participating, even though they may be excluded from some tasks.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text is concerned with the spiritual welfare of the initiates and the group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, there are other indications that new scribes were educated for writing and reading.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Notes: However, special knowledge is attributed to the community and its leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: However, the community and its leaders were predominantly, if not exclusively, male. Yet IQSa speaks of gathering all Israel, including women and children for the hearing of the teaching.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Notes: However, IQS has elsewhere a ratio of one priest in every group of ten.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The initiates are instructed to follow the teachings of the priests, Levites, and larger community group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: The special knowledge of the community ensures blessings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Notes: However, blessings and curses as well as confession of sins follow familiar texts from the Torah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: Elsewhere in the Dead Sea Scrolls, a war between the "Sons of Light" and the "Sons of Darkness" is described.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Bibliography

General References

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